

Socio-economic Profile of Indigenous Koch Community: A Study in Gazipur District, Bangladesh

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Abstract

Bangladesh, a densely populated country, situates in South-Asia holding approximately forty-five indigenous communities from the very beginning of human civilization. Among different indigenous communities, the Koch is one of them which has been considered as the most morphemes one, prevailing multiple variations. Based on historical account that the Koch community has been residing in Bangladesh since one thousand and three hundred years ago in various places especially, in Rangpur, Dinajpur, Naogaon, Netrokona, Mymansingh and largely in Gazipur district. In contrast to other indigenous communities, the Koch community is deeply found as vulnerable, distressed, illiterate, impoverish with physical and mental disorder. Almost, all the Koch communities are habited to face with unhygienic environment as well as rustic social values living in Gazipur district. They are regarded as the Koch community only by birth and they are totally deprived of getting proper education, cultural practice, political involvement, economic and social status including healthcare and cure. They are also totally unable to raise their voices because of having different obstacles. The aim of the study was to know the socio-economic profile of the Koch community in different segments of their lives and livelihoods. We used household survey along with in-depth interviews of thirty participants to collect primary data along with reviewing some specific literature related to the topic. The findings of the study revealed that Koch indigenous people are getting gradually marginalized, underprivileged, under pressured, disadvantaged, bearing backward socio-cultural practices, lack of fundamental human rights and family needs and necessities, impoverish health status as well as curing practices. Their present socio-economic and

cultural conditions do not deserve their own history and heritage. They are socially excluded to survive for their lives and livelihoods because of illiteracy, lack of awareness, traditional knowledge and customs, in comparison with other communities.

Keywords: Koch Community, Traditional attitude, Socio-economic, Hunting and Gathering, Underprivileged.

Introduction

a) Understanding to the Study Community

Bangladesh is located in South Asia. It borders both India and Myanmar and areas is 1,44,000 Square kilometers. In addition to the general population there are more than 54 indigenous communities in Bangladesh, and they speak at least 35 different languages. Only 30 of this communities are on government records (Kashem,2007). The country's indigenous population as reported by the census in 2022, is estimated to be 16, 50,4,78 (BBS, 2022), or 1% of the total population. However, according to the country's indigenous peoples, there are about 4 million of them (Barkat, 2015). The Chittagong Hill Tracts (CHT) are home to the remaining indigenous people, while the plains districts of the country are home to the majority of them (Halim, 2015). Historically, the indigenous people have been living with the Bengalis in many areas of the country maintaining peace and holding their heritage based on geographical and ethnic features, as many as 350 million ethnic communities live worldwide and have many ways of living (ECDO, 2007). According to the Ambassador of European Union to Bangladesh (Charles, 2024), In 90 countries across the world, there are more than 476 million indigenous people making up 6.2% of the total population. Indigenous people, however, assert that there are roughly 5 million of them. The plain land districts in the country's north and southeast are home to about 80% of the indigenous population, while the remaining individuals reside in the Chittagong Hill tracts (CHT) (Zaman et al., 2019). According to the estimation of Bangladesh Adivasi Forum (indigenous people forum), a top advocacy and networking organization of the ethnic minorities, at least 3 million indigenous people live in Bangladesh (BIPF,2019). Even, in the low land areas many minority groups dwell in Bangladesh retaining their distinct ethnic traits, social institutions, religious organizations, cultural traditions, self-medication and traditional healing practices at home with their indigenous knowledge.

The recently approved, Small Ethnic Minority Cultural Institution Act (April 2010) has mentioned nearly 27 different groups currently under revision and suggests 50 other groups. Bangladesh Indigenous Peoples' Rights Act 1997 (Republic Act no. 8371 of 1997) also mentioned that ethnic minority groups have lived in around 59 districts of the country (TPDP, 2017). Some other researchers

also have shown approximately 75 indigenous communities in Bangladesh (Gain, 2011). Since the independence of Bangladesh (1971), the indigenous communities have been striving to get their identities recognized by the state. Even, Bangladesh has not adopted the UN declaration on the rights of indigenous peoples and the social, economic, political and modern health rights of the country's indigenous peoples remain ignored (The indigenous world, 2024). The indigenous peoples are scattered in various parts of the country. They live in several geographical pockets. Their lifestyles are very colorful and there is a strong emphasis on culture and heritage in their respective communities. Most of the indigenous people live in hill districts, coastal zones and low lands areas of our country. Some indigenous communities also live in the plain lands in many districts including Gazipur. Around eight ethnic groups live in Gazipur (Nunia, Vangor, Bouna, Chedi, Manipuri, Garo, Santal & Koch) where Koch indigenous people are the highest in numbers (Ahmed,2001). Many Koch people have been living in Gazipur Sadar, Kaliakoir, Kapasia, Sreepur and many other parts of deep jungle areas of the district. Koch peoples are scattered in the northern and northwestern part of Gazipur district specially Pingail, Sitpara, Hatiyab, Bonogram, Noulapara, Haldoba, Monipur, Madhapara, Manipur Kashpara, Bikebari, Katlamara, Taltoli, Dighdha Uttar Para, Barhar, ChokBarhar, Kumarkhada, Ghilagasia, Ranipur, Lutirchala, Noyapara/Asromchala, Andanmanik, Berabari village, and many other places (Bormon,2010). But the government has no actual statistics about the number of Koch people in the Gazipur district (Ahmed,2001). Koch people have been facing different socio-economic problems and suffering greatly in different aspects of their lives and livelihoods that ultimately affect their socio-cultural life, indigenous medicine, health, and healthcare seeking behavior. They are underprivileged regarding their fundamental health rights and women's health issues, particularly reproductive health.

The Koch people are among the earliest indigenous groups in the Gazipur district. Approximately 1300 years ago, the small-ethnic Koch community departed their ancestral homeland Koch Bihar, India, because of oppression, persecution, famine, communal rioting. They have since settled in the Gazipur district, which was then known as the Bhawal region. Although some have returned over time, the re-judgment took place in the nineteenth century. In 1914, they relocated to the Bhawal region after a famine struck their previous habitation (Ahmed,2001). Historian Jatindra Mohan Roy said that the decline of the dynasty started from the time of Damodar. As a result, the Koches started occupying many places like Madhupur and Bhawal region in Bangladesh. It is believed that Koches are the descendants of kings of Kochbihar, Nara Narayan and Chita Roy. It is also believed that the Koch is originated from the part of central Asia that is now as known as Tibet, (Nath, 1989) a mountainous region in Asia on the northern side of the Himalayas.

According to Vijaykumar (1369 Bangla at Protiva Newspaper), the Koch indigenous people arrived in Bangladesh during monarch Harishchandra and Damodar's period. The first half of the seventeenth century was directly govern by Harishchandra and the second half of the time it was govern by Damodar. Therefore, it can be claim that a large number of Koch people have migrated to Bangladesh over time, primarily from India, due to their varied cultural beliefs customs, behaviours, and values. They have been relating mainstream societies to deal with the advent of nature from the very beginning of human civilization.

b) Background of the Study

Historically, Gazipur is an environmentally amicable district for indigenous people that supports their way of life. Among all the indigenous people who they have been living here Koch are the most renowned. They came here thousands of years ago and been have living peacefully with some other indigenous peoples. They are one of the most ancient ethnic communities in this district where they do live in minimum fifty-one (51) villages with their self-identities in north-central and north-eastern region of the district.

The Koch of Bangladesh live in a small pocket of land, who have different geographical, political and socio-economic ways of living. Koch people always like to stay very close to nature. Besides, they like to go frequently jungle for hunting and gathering in a group to collect families' foods, needs and necessities. Most of the Koch people have lost and transferred their living places and own lands by the pressure of local Bengali elite people, aggression by land encroachers, making of industrial factories and recreational centers. At present, majority of Koch are landless and few of them have a little land. Their life style is very much struggling, but they have been living in a uniform mode by their own community. Though, they do not have any educational institute related to their own language and culture. They have their own socio-cultural history, heritage and traditions and also they have their own rituals and belief, songs, quiz, proverb, folk song, poems and myths. They live along with their area with cultural heritage, religious values, traditional farming, herbal and indigenous system of taking treatment and medicine. They believe in Sanatan Hindu religion. But they have some exceptional religious activities in compare to Hinduism too. During Funeral, if the Koch people die of Cholera or Pox their dead body is floated on the water (Haque, 2002). In Hinduism this ritual is not seen. As a traditional culture they also celebrate Charok Puja (devotion to Gods in Hinduism) at every Pohela Baishakh month in Bangla year (1st day of Bengali New year). Almost all the Koch use to lead their lives below the poverty line. They have been struggling with low household incomes and dependency on cultivation as a major source of revenue (Rahman, et. al. 2012) and are getting gradually marginalized and disadvantaged in different sphere of real life. Their family pattern, marriage system,

inheritance laws, norms and values, habitation, housing, social structure, language, economy, religion, beliefs and healthcare are different from other indigenous community and of course not consistent with the tradition of mainstream Bangladeshi common people (Chakma,2002). The Koches are usually accustomed to living in deep forests divided into groups or sub-groups. They believe that when they lived in their original home (in the Hajo region of India) there were no groups or sub-groups. However, based on the historical background, it can be seen that there are various groups or sub-groups of Koch community in the evolutionary trend of time. Linguist Grierson speaks of six clans or subgroups of Koch. These are: Harganj /Harigaiya, Satpair /Satpari, Dashgaiya or Banai, Chapra, Wana/Wanang, and Tentakia or Tintikia (Islam, 2005). According to Subash Jengcham book “Indigenous Peoples” which was published by the Bangladesh Asiatic Society, there are seven distinct groups within the indigenous Koch community. The teams are Wanang, Harigaiya, Satpari, Dashgaiya, Chapra Tinzekiya and Shankar. In Bangladesh, there is also a small group of koches named Morgan, who live in a village called Daodhara in Nalitabari police station in Sherpur district (Zengcham, 2014). Each of the branches or teams mentioned above has a number of clans. The Koches call all these tribes Nikni/Nikini. The number of such Koches or nicknames of Koches is more than a hundred.

Indigenous people play an important role in controlling their social life. When any kind of social problem arises within the Koch community, the elders create a way to solve all the problems in harmony. Among the Koches, the status of senior citizens of all castes is much higher. In the Koch community, on the other hand only Tintikia Koches are considered to have the lowest social status; however, they are still carrying the social customs, rules, language, culture, history-tradition, Pujaparvan of the original identity of the Koches in the socio-cultural adverse situation. Some association related to tribal people’s which development have also been working on those grounds (BIPF, 2020). For this reason, mutual relationship sympathy and solidarity are very deep in the Koch society. From ancient times, the Koches have been living happily and harmoniously with other indigenous groups. But, although some research works and books exist on different castes and tribes living in Bangladesh, no significant research book has been found on the indigenous Koch people of Gazipur district. No documentary evidence of accurate data on the population of the indigenous Koch community of the district is available which is extremely unfortunate for the protection of a backward and near to extinct indigenous community like them. In this point of view, in order to understand the unique socio-economic conditions of this indigenous community, this research might play an important role so far.

c) Community Profiling and Mapping of the Research Site

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to determine the socio-economic well-beings and sorrows of Koch community living in Gazipur district in Bangladesh.

Some specific objectives of the study are-

- a) To understand the study populations socio-demographic features;
- b) To have knowledge about their employment, economy and challenges of life and livelihoods;
- c) To understand the nature of their traditions, rituals and beliefs.

Methodology

The research is based on both quantitative and qualitative data. For quantitative data we conducted a household survey and for qualitative data in-depth interviews with thirty (30) participants were

conducted in the research areas from different household. Qualitative tools such as Focus-group discussions (FGDs) and a questionnaire was used in data collection, which was appropriately finalized through pre-testing. Some related data were collected through observatory method. We reviewed related literature for secondary data also. The study area was purposively selected on the basis of socio-economic, socio-cultural condition and vulnerability of the people. Populations of the study were all Koch Community's people who are living in the Pingail village of Gazipur district. The study respondents for in-depth interviews were also selected purposively considering their knowledge, ability and willingness to provide information.

Findings and Discussions

In this section, the findings of the research and discussion have been presented. Cooperation was sought with the help of concerned people living around the study area. The participants were voluntarily cooperated in providing information. The findings and discussion of the research are presented with quantitative and qualitative way in several sections below-

Demographic Information of the participants

Table No. 01:

Sl	Age (yr)	Religion	Educational Qualification	Family Pattern	Family Member	Marital Status	Migration from
1	36	Sanatan Hindu	Graduate	Nuclear	04	Married	Kuchbon forest, India
2	23	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-6)	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown
3	24	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-7)	Nuclear	02	Married	Unknown
4	26	Sanatan Hindu	Graduate (Hon's)	Nuclear	03	Married	Middle-East
5	52	Sanatan Hindu	Illiterate	Nuclear	04	Married	Unknown
6	50	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-6)	Nuclear	06	Married	Kochbihar, India
7	24	Sanatan Hindu	Graduate (Final year)	Extend	08	Married	Mandar Hill, Kochbihar, India
8	40	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-6)	Nuclear	04	Married	Unknown
9	21	Sanatan Hindu	S.S.C.	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown
10	30	Sanatan Hindu	Praimary	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown

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11	19	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-8)	Extend	07	Married	Unknown
12	75	Sanatan Hindu	Illiterate	Nuclear	03	Married	Kuchbon forest, India
13	40	Sanatan Hindu	Prainary	Nuclear	04	Married	Mandar Hill, Kochbihar, India
14	24	Sanatan Hindu	S.S.C.	Nuclear	05	Married	Assam state, India
15	35	Sanatan Hindu	Prainary	Nuclear	04	Married	Savar
16	49	Sanatan Hindu	Prainary	Nuclear	04	Married	Permanent residence in Pingail
17	47	Sanatan Hindu	Know how to read and write	Nuclear	02	Married	Dinajpur
18	45	Sanatan Hindu	Prainary	Nuclear	04	Married	Kochbihar, India
19	100+	Sanatan Hindu	Illiterate	Extend	07	Married	Mandar Hill, Kochbihar, India
20	70	Sanatan Hindu	Know how to read and write	Nuclear	03	Married	Kochbihar, India
21	21	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-7)	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown
22	73	Sanatan Hindu	Illiterate	Extend	06	Married	Kochbihar, India
23	55	Sanatan Hindu	Know how to read and write	Nuclear	03	Married	Savar
24	65	Sanatan Hindu	Illiterate	Extend	07	Married	Unknown
25	26	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-6)	Nuclear	04	Married	Unknown
26	47	Sanatan Hindu	Illiterate	Extend	05	Married	Madhupur, Tangail
27	29	Sanatan Hindu	Know how to read and write	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown
28	27	Sanatan Hindu	Prainary	Nuclear	06	Married	Unknown
29	27	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-8)	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown

30	28	Sanatan Hindu	Secondary (class-10)	Nuclear	03	Married	Unknown
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The above data revealed that all the participants follow Hindu religion and their family pattern is nuclear (80%) and extend (20%). Their minimum educational qualification is knowing how to read and write (13.33%), Primary level (20%), class six to ten (30%), SSC (6.67%), graduate level (10%) and rest of them are illiterate (20%). The ages of all the participations were between 19 to 103 years. Average family size of the participants consists of 05 members. The research revealed that most of participants (46.67%) don't know where they have come from in Pingail. The large number of participants (33.33%) came in Pingail from several states of India, only a single participant (3.33%) came from Middle East, 3.33% from Tangail, 3.33% from Dinajpur, 6.67% from Savar, remaining 3.33% is a permanent resident of Pingail.

Occupational Status

Table No. 02:

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Agriculture	15	23.81
Animal Husbandry	05	7.93
Day labor	03	4.76
Garments Worker	02	3.17
Housewife	18	28.57
Hunting & Gathering	02	3.17
Livestock	09	14.28
Plant seller	01	1.59
Service (Private)	02	3.17
Student	01	1.59
Teaching	01	1.59
Traditional Healer	01	1.59
Wood collector & seller	03	4.76
	N= 63*	100
* Multiple answer		

Their ancient profession was agriculture, fishing, hunting, gathering, weaving cloths, bamboo and cane work and wood collection. They also engaged in selling and making houses by hardened mud, traditional healing, carpenter, singing and livestock. At present socio-economic and socio-cultural changes, the Koch women do some other works with their ancient profession. Like- Teaching, garments worker, Private service, plants seller, day laborers, students. Even if, from the information of their ancestors their husbands' profession is changing rapidly. Like- small business, resort caretaker, rickshaw pulling, singing and playing.

Income Generation and Expenditure

Table-03

Income	Frequency	Percentage(%)
150-249	07	23.33
250-349	06	20
350-449	06	20
450-549	06	20
550-649	02	6.67
650-749	03	10
	N = 30	100

The daily income structure shows that their economic situation extensively decreased and expenditure is equal to. There is no mentionable amount of money had been found in income sector of Koch community. They do not have much opportunity for permanent income so, in Pingail village percentage of low income peoples is very high. Most of the families (23.33%) per-day income is taka 150 to 249. 10% families per-day income of the highest amount of taka 650 to 749 only.

Daily expenditure of the participants' family

Table-04

Expenditure	Frequency	Percentage(%)
200-299	08	26.67
300-399	11	36.67
400-499	03	10
500-599	05	16.66
600-699	00	00
700-799	03	10
	N = 30	100

Fulfillment the family's necessities

Table
-05

Answer	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	10	33.33
No	20	66.67
	N = 30	100

Majority of the participants (66.67%) couldn't fulfil all their necessities by their present income.

Because of their-

- ❖ Poor income,
- ❖ Depend on traditional agro-farming
- ❖ Lost of forest resources becoming narrower and being grabbed, deforestation, and burning of forests by fire.

□ In the opposite scenario it is seems that, only 33.33% can support the family with their monthly income, cause of-

- ❖ They are little bit educated
- ❖ Aware and alert
- ❖ Permanent employees
- ❖ Classical farmers and businessman and
- ❖ Most of them are associated with many professions besides holding on their ethnic profession.

Sources of Drinking Water

Most of the participants (73%) source of drinking water is tube-well. A little portion of the participants (3%) use deep tube-well water from time to time and 7% participants used drinking water from neighbor houses. 17% participants use on submersible water. Though, all of the participants used safe drinking water but majority of the participants have not self water resources. They depend on other. Sometimes, participant used to get drinking water walk at least half or one kilometer. They use to walk through peoples house, and crop field.

Types of Sanitation which they use

Table-06

Types	Frequency	Percents (%)
Pacca	04	13.33
Semi-Pacca	02	6.67
Kacha	16	53.33
Temporary	03	10
Shared Latrine	05	16.67
	N= 30	100

Sanitation is deeply related to health and hygiene in every community. Participants used five types of latrine which are Pacca (13.33%), Semi-pacca (6.67%), Kacha (53.33%), temporary (10%) and rest of participants (16.67%) used shared latrines. Many Koch women suffered from various diseases as used of unsanitary Kacha latrine and poor hygiene. So, they effected diseases such as-dysentery, cholera, typhoid and starworm. The people of pingail areas are mostly ignorant on how to use safe water and sanitary latrines.

Social Structure and Resources

Table No. 07:

Name of Structure and Resources	Total number(s)
Households	298
Residential units	05
Dighi (lake)	01
Ponds	05
Mondir (tomb)	04
Social club	02
Govt.primary school	01
Grocery shops	11
Smal market (excluding grocery shops)	01
Bazar (nearby village)	01

Source: Household Survey and observation

While conducting social survey and observation in the study area, the study team found some socio-economic, religious and institutional structure. The study area is divided into 5 (five) residential unit (para/shomaj). Pingail villages has many resources like-digi, pond, mondir (tomb), roads, agriculture land, club and deep forest. They also have natural medicinal plants, pig, urchin, rat, snakes, tortoise and animal husbandry for their livelihoods. There is a govt. primary school where the children of Koch community along with other Bengali community have been studying. Eleven (11) small grocery shops are seen at many various spots. The Bhabanipur bazar (village market) is the only place where

the villagers buy and sell the products they need every day. They also have a small market in the middle point of the village beside Green Tech Eco Resort.

Socio-Cultural Organizations

During household survey and observation, it was revealed that Koch people living in under privileged, back ward, rustic and remote area. But they are very much organized and following a unique culture. The Tribal Welfare Association's (T.W.A) branch office is established in the year 2010 located at Pingail village. The association tries to attach indigenous people with their traditional housing pattern, traditional music and marriage system. The association is engaged in working on their own areas and tries to protect their language, education, history and heritage. Beside Bangladesh Adibasi Forum (BAF) is another ethnic related community association that is working for the promotion and protection of the rights of indigenous people of this region.

Housing and Shelter

It was found that almost all the Koch houses are generally made of straw, banana leaf, coconut tree leaves, climber, bamboo and fence made of cane, wood, mud and tin while observing the area by the research team. At present, some tin-shed buildings are also found which are built with the help of their local carpenters. Their living room are very much congested. Latrines or toilets are far away from main house. Kitchen is built beside the main house keeping short distance from the home. They make a round wall of their living houses for outdoor protection made by bamboo and banana leaf. Usually Koch people collect housing materials from nearby natural forest. Koch people live in their own close group in a square based house. Their houses have all been unplanned and housing structure is very fragile but neat and clean. Their living room is very small where many people live together. Local 'Sayyal' or 'Karikar' (carpenters) made their houses and small room for domestic animals. In essence, the housing structures of pingail village are poorly designed and constructed. The construction of the households is not only *kancha* but also very extreme poor quality. There is another type of shelter room which is called *Jhupris*. *Jhupris* are commonly found in such every houses. The prime features of the indigenous Koch people's houses are low in height and very small in space or size.

Religious and Social Values

All the populations of this study area believe in Sonatan (Hindu) religion bearing the identities of Borman.

One participant while taking in depth interview, described as,

We believe in Sonatan religion under Kshatriya (noble) caste just a step inferior to Borman (priest). Four temples in the village have been to perform Hinduism. We are pious in performing all our religious activities. As a traditional culture we celebrate Charok Puja (devotion to Gods in Hinduism) at every Pohela Baishak in Bangla (1st day of Bengali New Year) every year as our main festival.

There were social classes and aristocracy in Koch communities based on religious caste. But by the passage of time, there is no existence of social classes in the Koch communities. The participants were

also aware of their social values. In this regard a participant told, Pingail is a perfectly peaceful village with five residential shomaj (social unit). They like to live very peaceful and cooperative life. Helping to one another is their traditional habit. They respect their elderly and pious people and lead a very simple life in the noise free areas. In each para (village) there is a Matubbar (chief) who solved the community's problems and we all honor his decision.

One of the senior participant described as,

Koches are always united in all activities. With our own identities we serve our level best to our society. The people of this community do not like to live outside the community as many cases. We are excluded from the Bengali societies but we enjoy our pain and pleasure all together.

Traditional Healing

Koch people generally believe in taking traditional treatment. They use to go to Kabiraj (herbal healer) and Ujha (spiritual healer) for their treatment. In this regard one of the participants described as,

We do not avail healthcare facilities from the govt. and NGOs'clinic but very easily take treatment from our Kabiraj. They provide treatment based on herbal plants and other medicines collected from the forests.

Another participant expressed his opinion about spiritual treatment as,

Our people go to the Ujha (spiritual healer) for taking their treatment through spirit. We like to herbs medicine and have to take such kind of treatment to protect ourselves from mental and physical diseases. Some people use black magic for evil desire. Spirit helps us to be saved ourselves from them.

Water and Utility Services

In our observation, Koch villagers by themselves have made a greater contribution by establishing the tube-well in the Pingail village. From the recent past they have been using unsafe drinking water but now-a-days the water and utility resource facilities are positively changing the village of Pingail where the Koch people live in.

While asking a participant in-depth interviews, he expressed his opinion as,

Most of villagers for cleaning clothes, bathing, dish washing, animal husbandry, organic farming and so many are dependent on the water resources. But we are not satisfied much with the quality of natural water resource facilities and services. We came to know from our ancestors that causally most of the Koch people affected by the water diseases like Cholera, Diarrhea, dysentery by drinking ponds and tank water before many years ago. Then after all, we think that they should drink fresh water from tube-well for our life safety.

Another participant added about the present utility services of the study area as,

Afterwards 02 (two) tube-well have been setup in the Koch villages East and North-west side. Another tube-well is situated at the Pingail govt. primary school field. After 47 (forty-seven) years of independences, for the first time, we got electricity facilities in the month of March, 2017. On the other side, there is no significant gas service for us.

Ceremonial Activities

Koch communities follow different marriage, funeral and other cultural ceremony. There is no uniform marriage and divorce law in Koch communities and marriages those are dominated by the society and cultural rules. They do not arrange marriage in the Bengali month of Vadro, Poush and Chaittra.

One of the participants described as,

Our Para (unit) chief approves the date of marriage consulting the related families. We do not allow love marriage and sex relationship before marriage. Even we do not permit marriage within the same cast. In our marriage ceremony, we follow the traditional Hindu culture and customs. Divorce and widow remarriage are accepted in our communities.

A most senior participant described about the funeral of dead bodies as,

While anyone died in Koch communities, we perform many rituals for the happiness of dead soul. Getting our relatives' death message, we all go to show respect to the dead body. The dead bodies are burnt and after the burning of dead body, the family members or relatives collect the bones and rest of the burnt bodies, because they believe that their success lies in it. and usually, the religious leader's bodies are interred under the soil. If anybody dies of some exceptional diseases like cholera and or pox, the dead body is floated on rivers or canals.

Hunting and gathering

The Koches perform hunting and gathering for their survivals from the very beginning of their civilization. They are skilled unit and learned how to hunt and gather from the nature from their ancestors. But it is a matter of very pity that they do not have as many natural forests as they have before. As a result, the source of natural foods is decreasing day by day.

One of the participants told about it as,

Rabbits, pigs, rabbits, crabs, tortoises, quails, snails, wild boars, pigeons and bucks are some of the traditional foods we had before, but almost all these animal habitats are being destroyed. Contaminated water from mills is causing huge damage to agricultural lands and open water bodies. Besides, valuable plants are being removed from the forest. We don't get animals and birds in the forest like before. In our traditional food culture, the festival of hunting various animals including rabbits, rabbits and pigs is no more. Earlier on moon lit night, the older male members of the family used to hunt animals all night long in groups in the deep jungle divided into semi-groups with nets, arrows, bows and spears. At present we do not get enough animals and fishes except rabbits and cuchia (eels).

Another participant delivered his speech about hunting and gathering as,

Once, some varieties of forest vegetables as traditional foods were favorites among the ethnic Koches. One of them is long black wild potato (Jongli Alu) and another one is trees potato (Gaicha Alu), Wild potatoes were produced under the ground and Gaicha potatoes were produced on the top of tall leaf-like trees. Those are our traditional and popular foods which we cook with fish and poultry.

One of the participants who hunts and gathers from the jungles described as,

Even now-a-days we collect soil potato by digging with the help of wild picks and with the help of tall bamboo, we collect the trees potato. I could get maximum 10/12 kg of potatoes by working all day in the field. At present, this delicious natural food is becoming scarce in the forests. Sometimes we eat 'Kachi bash Koral' (made of tender bamboo) curry and 'Kainjal' bhaji (made of banana tree) as traditional food and entertain the guests.

Traditional foods and meals

Koch communities of Gazipur district have been processed with traditional food habits. They prefer traditional foods in their home to junk foods.

One of the participants said that,

We have a variety of traditional foods. One of the traditional dishes is "Kakathamuri" which is made of mixing rice, dried fish, slices of special leaf collected from the jungles, green chilies in sufficient quantity and salt in hot water. 'Pithali' (Cake) is another kind of delicious food which is made with mixing fish, rice powder, raw chili, ginger powder, onion and other spices. These dishes are usually served at Bandurga Punja (worship/devotion), special Puja-Parvan (season of worship) and wedding ceremonies. 'Banana leaves' are used instead of plates when serving food to guests.

Another participant described as,

Puli pitha, chitai pitha, bhapa pitha, tal pitha, rice kheer, (all are the name of some cakes) raw date juice kheer, payes, khai, batasha and sweet national foods are our traditional food during various festivals and ceremonies. Sometimes we serving these foods to our relatives and guests. All of our traditional food preparation ingredients are no longer available. Day by day the traditional foods are getting lost from the menu. As a result, our traditional food culture can no longer be maintained.

Another participant told as,

Cholai mod (traditional wine) has been one of our traditional beverages since ancient times. Usually we make this kind of drink at home by decomposing rice and molasses. During any social or religious occasion we serve wine to the guests and everyone enjoys it very well. Moreover, other fruit drinks, palm and date juice is one of our most popular drinks. We make 'tari' (one kind of alcohol) with the sound of taal (music) and take it ourselves and serve it to others. All these traditional drinks are still available in our sherbet (society).

The above study findings on the socio-economic profile of Koch Community of Gazipur district reflect the actual and present reality of the study communities lives and livelihoods. Though once, Koch people were enriched with their social status, culture and heritage, wealth and prosperity, slowly they have been losing everything because of socio-cultural, geo-political and ethnical causes. Their traditional socio-economic activities and rituals have no more ability to fight against those of Bengali communities. For these reasons, the participants' occupational status, housing patterns, social values, habit of taking foods and meals are changing gradually.

Conclusion and recommendations

From the very beginning of Koch civilization, they have been struggling to form their own culture, custom and ways of lives and livelihoods to hold their existence. Now they are legged behind from

the Bengali socio-cultural and economic activities because of their illiteracy, discrimination, exclusion by the nontribal peoples and taboos from tribal sheik chiefs. So, any kind of discrimination or exclusion of Koches along with irritating their own ways of lives and livelihoods should be disallowed to make a comprehensive and inclusive social construction. As a rapid developing country, Bangladesh would like to stand before the world as a rich nation by 2041 with comprehensive and inclusive criteria in development area. To reach this ambitious tower all the nontribal peoples including ethnic populations take pride in showing their own identities in participating in all the developing activities as the citizens of this nation. The Koch communities are also trying to contribute in various socio-economic activities keeping their own traditional and tribal values. Now it is our duty to keep them socially and economically sound in their own circumstances for national integration to achieve SDGs by 2030, second perspective plan by 2041 and all other plans of the government. In this regard the following points are recommended.

1. Bottom up policy is required about the study populations' socio-economic emancipation and political empowerment for their inclusion in every sector in the greater society.
2. Proper steps might be taken on the matters of ecosystem and biodiversity for protecting the natural forests for tribal peoples' traditional and economic activities which is much related to better life and livelihoods of the study populations living there. (a) To discover the pattern of biodiversity, information on it has to be collected and (b) as some species living there play vital roles in ecosystem, study might be carried out on the topic also.
3. Activities should be carried out on the preservation of the valuable traditional culture and heritage as they are the diametrical needs of the study population so far.
4. Religious values should be implemented so that they may be able to uphold their spiritualities with a view to perform a moral life and lifestyle.

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